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On behalf of the Organizing and Scientific Committee, We are pleased to welcome you all at the 5th International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2020 Novi Sad.

The Scientific and Organization Committee have made every effort to plan a conference that is scientifically satisfactory and interesting, although it is held on-line due to pandemic situation caused by COVID -19.

You will be met with an exceptional program covering different topics, from basic research areas to areas within daily practice of Restorative Dentistry, Endodontics, Prosthodontics, Oral Surgery and Implantology, Periodontology, Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry.

We really hope that next year these uncertain times will be behind us, and that you will have opportunity to experience the traditional hospitality of Novi Sad, to strengthen the existing friendships and create a lot of new ones.

President of the Organizing Committee

Prof. dr Tatjana Puskar

President of the Scientific Committee

Assist. Prof dr Milica Jeremic Knezevic

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PAIN IN TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract: *Temporomandibular disorders-TMD are a common type of musculoskeletal disorder in the orofacial region involving the masticatory muscles, temporomandibular joint (TMJ) and associated structures. The typical features are pain in TMJ, restriction of mandibular movement, TMJ sound, and facial deformities. The prevalence of pain in temporomandibular joint in general population lies in the range of about 5-12%.*

Persistent pain in the masticatory muscles is usually unilateral condition, may be exacerbated by normal oral function such as chewing, talking, or yawning. Limited mouth opening-less than 30-35mm and deviation to the affected side are present. Both tenderness and trigger points in muscles are also characteristics of these pain.

Therapy of TMD are reversible and irreversible.

Specialized physical therapy options such as ultrasound, iontophoresis, electrotherapy, or low-level laser therapy have been used in the management of TMD.

If the patient has a restricted opening- stretching the mouth wider. This is usually performed by placing the index finger over the incisal edges of the mandibular incisors and the thumb over the incisal edges of the maxillary incisors and pressing the teeth apart by moving the fingers in a scissor-type motion.

NSAIDs are first-line agents typically used for 10 to 14 days for initial treatment of acute pain. Patients with suspected early disk displacement, synovitis, and arthritis benefit from early treatment with NSAIDs. Despite the multiple choices of NSAIDs available, only naproxen (Naprosyn) has proven benefit in reduction of pain. Muscle relaxants can be prescribed with NSAIDs if there is evidence of a muscular component to TMD.

Opioids are not recommended and, if prescribed, should be used for a short period in the setting of severe pain for patients in whom nonopiate therapies have been ineffective. Even with these parameters, opioids should be used cautiously because of the potential for dependence.